

INFORMATION LITERACY SKILLS AND LIBRARY RESOURCES USE BY STUDENTS IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN OYO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Library resources use benefits among secondary school students cannot be underestimated. The use of library resources by students in secondary schools contributes their academic performance but it is quite unfortunate that some of the students do not use the library or sparingly use the library to develop themselves. Empirically studies exist in support of information literacy skills and library resources use among students but it is not apparent that a study in public secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. Therefore, this study investigated the influence of information literacy skills on library resources use by students in public secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. The study adopted survey research with population of 5325 and sample size of 361 was selected using Krejcie and Morgan sample size table. The Cronbach Alpha coefficient ranges from 0.78 to 0.87. The findings showed that information literacy skills have a significant influence on library resources use by public secondary school students in Oyo State ($Adj. R^2 = 0.124$, $F(4,356) = 13.792$, $p < 0.05$). The findings show that novel, textbook and database are the library resources used more while most of the students use the library for the purpose of preparing for examination, to read note and to prepare ahead of the class. The study concluded that information literacy skills influences library resources use.

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INTRODUCTION

Library is known for the assemblage of knowledge in its entirety. Library provides scholarly and non-scholarly write up that exists in print and in non-print format carefully selected to meet the needs of the users. Libraries accommodate information resources required by the different groups of users. Library is derived the Latin word 'liber' which means 'book'. Library is a collection or group of collections of books and/or other print or non-print materials organized and maintained for use reading, consultation, study, research and personal development (American Library Association [ALA], 2025). Library serves as the nerve center of an educational institution and a place where information is provided to serve all patrons irrespective of their ages, political and ethical background, religion, educational qualification and gender (Tiemo & Ateboh, 2016). There are different types of libraries ranging from National, Public, Academic, Special, Virtual and School libraries. The emphasis of this study is on school library because it is the only library found in secondary schools with resources to meet the students and teachers need.

School library also known as school media centre is the library established to serve the information needs of nursery, primary and secondary school students and teachers (Ashikuzzaman, 2024). School library is a specialised learning environment within a school that provides access to a broad range of educational resources, including books, magazines, digital media and other reference materials (Idhalama, Abdullahi & Abubaka, 2020). Secondary school libraries prepare students for higher education by introducing them to research skills, academic resources, and the importance of effective information management (Nzewi, 2023). Beyond academic support, libraries instill in students the value of lifelong learning. They encourage students to explore their interests, pursue self-study, and develop behaviour of curiosity that extends throughout their lives. Library in a secondary school is an essential component of the learning environment. It supports academic development, promotes reading, nurtures critical thinking and research skills, and enriches the cultural and social experiences of students. It equips them with the tools and knowledge they need for academic success and personal growth.

Utilisation of school library resources by secondary school students is a necessity that should interest all stakeholders in the secondary school system (Chukwuji, Nwankwo, Gadanga, Sule & Yusuf, 2017). It must be noted that the degree of usefulness of school library resources depends on its maximum utilisation by students. It could be deduced that non-use school library with relevant information resources could affect studies. However, the study of Umuhuza and Unegbu (2021) establish that the use of library resources enhances the total use of library resources for teaching and learning. Thus, the use of library resources is the totality of making use of information resources in the library.

The use of library resources may not be accomplished without information literacy skills of users because it plays a role in locating information resources in the library. There are numerous resources or materials in the library but only a student who is information literate can access the right material that will satisfy his or her information need (Ladele, Madukoma & Alegbeleye, 2022). The possession of information skills such as effective searching, source evaluation, and citation, which are essential for academic success, could initiate a paradigm shift in improving library resources use through processes of acquiring necessary resources to satisfy the quest of library users.

It is evident that students' general academic wellbeing and fruitfulness depends on their utilisation of library resources (Esimone & Osuafor, 2023). Studies have shown that secondary school students have different attitudes toward learning, which can be expressed in hours spent on

study, skills, study goals and preference for information sources (Roche, Band, Cavender, Chamberi, Everall, Krajewski & Pavey, 2022; Udo & Ben, 2022; Bucu, Pagalilauan & Daquioag, 2023). As a result, the significance of study habits in students' use of library resources cannot be overstated. Students' study habits play a critical role in their academic achievement. This is because students can only remember what is in their memory. According to Aanu and Olatoye (2017), students who don't study sufficiently may find it difficult to pass tests, particularly if there are a lot of topics to cover and not enough time to get ready.

Secondary school students do not make use of library resources efficiently, there is likelihood of poor academic performance (Akole & Olatunji, 2023; Mesagan & Ibrahim, 2021; Ramad & Kitula, 2022). This can be connected with the fact that students may not be using the library resources to enhance their academic activities (Ladele, Madukoma & Alegbeleye, 2022). Library resources are essential components of students' needs for academic excellence. Makinde, Jiyane and Mugwisi (2020) were of the opinion that library resources are needed for intellectual development and that it can also help school library to plan ahead.

Information Literacy Skills (ILSs) are another element that this study suggests may have an impact on the use of library resources. This is due to the fact that information literacy is necessary for a fruitful academic career. According to Malanga (2017), the term "information literacy skills" refers to a set of abilities that, when possessed, enables information users to become lifelong independent learners. These abilities include critical thinking, ethics, computer literacy, media literacy, library literacy, and communication. Put differently, information literacy skills are information literacy that are perceived as a process of acquiring abilities that would help one become an information literate individual (Adekunle & Madukoma, 2022).

Similarly, information literacy skills are the capacities that allow people to "identify when information is needed and how to obtain, evaluate, and use information effectively," according to the Prakash and Naik, (2020), it is significant to note that, as a result of technological advancements in information and communication technology, there is an increase in the amount of information resources available. Because of this, a lot of secondary school libraries now have Internet access. Osinulu (2020) noted that because they lack the knowledge and abilities necessary to use contemporary technologies, potential users of new information resources do not take advantage of the resources that can be useful; thus. There is need for skill acquisition programme for students to acquire information literacy skills (Aduba, Obot & Baro, 2022). Similarly, the integration and procurement of electronic information resources into libraries necessitates that information users exhibit information literacy abilities in order to facilitate the effortless access and retrieval of those resources. This assertion is corroborated by earlier research, which found that certain variables, such as computer self-efficacy and information literacy skills (ILS), may affect users' attitudes toward making efficient use of electronic information resources (Prangya & Rabindra, 2017).

The underutilization of electronic information resources may stem from low computer self-efficacy, which may impede information users' eagerness to utilise the secondary school library's electronic resources efficiently, or from a lack of information literacy skills, which restricts one's ability to obtain and use information ethically. Obianuju and Osuafor (2023) noted that students' capacity to find and retrieve information is a transferable talent that is beneficial in their future endeavors and facilitate efficient and fruitful utilization of virtual learning resources. The researchers went on to say that today's academic achievement requires the capacity to investigate the digital world. Students are expected to utilise the secondary school library's electronic

resources effectively. Babarinde and Adesina, (2023) proposed that students need to learn and practice the information literacy skills required for the efficient use of the many digital technologies available to them. Students must therefore use their newly learned information literacy skills in order to access this source material.

Dapo-Asaju, Ekeh, Makinde and Ogungbo (2021) corroborated this by determining that having an abundance of information is not sufficient to build an information society, rather, what matters most is ability to possess the skills and abilities needed to use the library's resources, information resource users need to have the information literacy skills required in order to use the resources at their disposal efficiently. Additionally, users of information resources require not only a knowledge base but also exploration techniques in order to be able to react effectively to an ever-changing environment. These techniques can then be combined with other knowledge bases and applied practically in order to solve problems or make decisions.

Information literacy skills are required not only to maximize the use of information resources but also to advance knowledge. In addition, information literacy skills enhance use of library resources, research and decisions that are information based. Okike (2020) clarified that users are required to acquire information literacy skills as the use of print and electronic information resources increases. In a world where technology is pervasive, information literacy skills are crucial and can be enhanced by utilizing creative teaching methods. According to Julien (2018), information literacy skills enable users to make efficient and effective use of the library's information resources. Libraries are vital to the core mission of any secondary school and the resources provided and accessible to students are essential part of learning process. Through provision of appropriate learning resources, the library contributes to the quality of teaching and research.

Statement of the Problem

The school library plays important role in the grooming of pupils and students from a tender age. This library is established to guide the users towards getting adequate information sources relevant to the curriculum of public secondary school students. Researcher like Isreal (2020) observed that students in secondary schools do not effectively use the library resources in their learning activities with attendant poor academic performances. This has been shown to be evident in Senior School Certificate Examinations and Joint Admissions Matriculation Board examination where dismayed performance of students has been observed to be very poor. (Essien, Ekim & Essien, 2024). Information literacy skills are expected to improve the library resources use by students in public secondary schools. Students should acquire the relevant information skills to fulfill the purpose of learning. Information literacy skills and library resources use have been conducted among postgraduates in University of Ilorin (Fajonyomi, Bukar & Ambali, 2021). In a study conducted in Ghana by Adjei (2024) used a single variable which is use of library resources. Although, there are dearth of studies on the combined influence of information literacy skills as predictor of library resources use by public secondary school students. Thus, there exists research gap on how information literacy skills predict the use of library resources by secondary school students. Therefore, this study will investigate the influence of information literacy skills as predictors of library resources use by secondary school students in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Objective of the study

The main objective of this study is to investigate the influence of information literacy skills on library resources use by public secondary school students in Oyo State, Nigeria. The Specific

objectives are to:

- i. determine the level of the Information literacy skills of public Secondary school students in Oyo State, Nigeria;
- ii. identify the type of library resources use by public Secondary school students in Oyo State, Nigeria;
- iii. find out the purpose of library resources use by students in public Secondary school students in Oyo State, Nigeria; and
- iv. determine the influence of information literacy skills on library resources use by students in public Secondary school students in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study will provide answers to the following questions:

- i. What is the level of information literacy skills of students in public Secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria?
- ii. What are the types of library resources used by students in public Secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria?
- iii. What is the purpose of using library resources by students in public Secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

The null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance

H₀₁ Information literacy skills have no significant influence on use of library resources by students in public secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Scope of the study

This study focus on information literacy skills and library resources use by public secondary schools students in Oyo State, Nigeria. Information literacy skills in the study focused on identification, searching, evaluation and application of information for their future use. The library resources use was analysed based on the types of library resources use and purpose of library resources use was used. The study geographical scope is limited to public secondary schools in selected secondary schools in Ibadan North Local Government Area with eight schools randomly selected from 36 senior secondary schools. The target respondents are 361 final year Senior Secondary Students 3 (SSS 3). The respondents that participated in the study were all registered SSS 3 students of the selected public secondary schools, irrespective of gender, age or religion because they are considered to have library experience more than other range of students in the secondary school. All other categories of students were excluded from participating in the study because their library experience is limited and they are not final year students deemed to be preparing for external examinations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Library Resources Use

The School Library provides an equitable approach to information for students to use in their daily work, whether their purpose is for school success, to solve problems or to create new knowledge. However, a school library provides a quiet and social space for meeting and studying, providing support services and circulating materials that assist school study (Udoh & Luke, 2022). The basic roles of school libraries irrespective of stratum of education could include the following: sharing

expensive resources such as data bases, e-books and periodicals; preserving and organizing artifacts and ideas and thereby serving a critical cultural role; helps researchers in winning research grants and contracts especially in research intensive universities; libraries play a major role with their skills in improving the quality of research funding applications and thereby the institution becomes successful in winning the research income as enumerated by Victor-Aigbodion, 2021; Vuso, 2022, Opele and Adigun, 2023. The functions of the school libraries vary depending on the mission of the parent organisation they belong to, some common responsibilities of providing information, managing projects, departments, community relationships, reference curriculum, research, classroom support, keeping up with the trends and technology in the field of library and information science especially in this era of using ICT in secondary schools.

Over the past few decades, school libraries have seen major changes in their fundamental activities, which have increased their recognition. School librarians now perform a variety of functions, including information management, research, teaching, and bookkeeping. School library usage in the recent times is influenced by users' awareness and the availability of relevant resources. The understanding of information needs of students is critical to their educational development (Udoh & Luke, 2022) and the need to help students achieve the best in their curriculum. Therefore, secondary school students as library users visit the library to obtain appropriate and important up-to-date information in print and non-print forms for effective performance, learning and research that meets their information needs, and also allowing them to make important school decisions. The implication is that the library is a promoter of school excellence (Okeuhie et al., 2021).

School libraries provide several services such as Online Public Access Catalogues (OPACs) in which their collection's metadata resources are available online so that users can use a library management system to find books and other materials that are available in the library following an operation guideline (Anafo et al., 2020). The Internet of Things (IoT) is a network of interconnected computing devices, digital and mechanical machines, objects, animals, and people that can transfer information across a system without requiring human-to-human or human-to-PC communication and are assigned unique identifiers (UIDs) (Rouse, 2020). Bansal et al. (2018) state that a variety of infrastructures can be incorporated to improve the library's man-to-man or man-to-machine or machine-to-man functionality because libraries are complex organisations with interconnected parts. Attaching sensors allows for the control of library holdings, including books, journals, periodicals, and other resources.

School Library Resources Use

Library information resources refer to available materials in print and non-print form that supports the curricular and personal needs of users of libraries. These resources have been viewed as backbone of academic development. It includes any material in the library which is used to provide information to users. It also connotes presence of books and non-books materials in terms of their availability for use (Esan & Akporhonor, 2021). These resources may include journals (including e-resources), books, magazines, DVDs, audiotapes, film and newspapers. Library information resources are in various forms and could be accessed through various means (Mesagan & Ibrahim, 2021).

Awojobi and Uthman (2022) opined that the effective use of library collection justifies the value of these collection by the library community and that adequate provision of library resources can have positive influence on school success Onye (2016) observe that teaching, learning, research,

and other uses of library resources will be hampered without the adequate provision of the information resources by the library while Mubashrah et al. (2013) was of the opinion that the library should provide the necessary resources for support and improvement of the quality of education. According to Agbokhaodeoshobughie and Eshiemkhai, (2024), the availability and accessibility of information materials in libraries is relevant to their use; therefore, the relevance of their use must satisfy the student's needs.

Information Literacy Skills

Information skill is defined as the ability to plan and source for information without any barrier (Nwabueze et al., 2022). Similarly, the American Library Association (2000), defined information literacy as the ability to recognize when information is needed and ability to locate, evaluate, and use effectively the information needed. In other words, information literacy is the capacity of people to recognize their information needs; locate and evaluate the quality of information; store and retrieve information; make effective and ethical use of information, and apply information to create and communicate knowledge (Babalola et al., 2021; Ladele, et al., 2022; Nwabueze, et al., 2022; Adenariwo & Oketunji, 2023). Information literacy refers to the ability to access, evaluate, organize and use information from a variety of information sources (Ekong & Ekong, 2018).

According to Azubuiké (2016), information literacy is a competence, a set of skills possessed by an individual to interact with information through the use information resources in making rational decision. Furthermore, it is a vital ability for the modern information-intensive world, enabling personal, economic, social and cultural development. It is the ability to access, evaluate, organize, and use information in order to learn, problem-solve, make decisions in formal and informal learning contexts, at work, at home and in educational settings. In the field of library and information science, literacy skills are very vital to knowledge acquisition and its competence (Sahabi et al., 2021).

METHODOLOGY

Survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised all registered 5,325 Senior Secondary School 3 students from Ibadan North Local Government Areas with 36 senior secondary schools. The sample size of 361 was selected via stratified random sampling technique.

DATA ANALYSIS, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table 1 *Information Literacy Skills*

Information literacy skills	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)	Mean	SD
Identification					3.41	0.779
I can identify useful information resources	238(65.9)	110(30.5)		13(3.6)	3.59	0.678
I can compare information from various sources	205(56.8)	139(38.5)	6(1.7)	11(3)	3.49	0.684
I can identify various view points of the topic from textbook	188(52.1)	131(36.3)	25(6.9)	17(4.7)	3.36	0.808

I can use information techniques such as search engines and online databases for studying.	184(51)	133(36.8)	27(7.5)	17(4.7)	3.34	0.812
I can identify the quality of a textbook good enough for my study	191(52.9)	111(30.7)	32(8.9)	27(7.5)	3.29	0.914
Searching					3.34	0.899
I am confident in using phones/ electronic tools to search for information	201(55.7)	137(38)	7(1.9)	16(4.4)	3.45	0.744
I am aware of search techniques (Boolean operators, truncation, etc.) to enhance my search process.	235(65.1)	65(18)	34(9.4)	27(7.5)	3.41	0.939
I am proficient in using search tools to find relevant information (e.g. databases).	202(56)	102(28.3)	29(8)	18(7.8)	3.32	0.921
I am proficient in using computer devices to search for books and online databases	209(57.9)	83(23)	43(11.9)	26(7.2)	3.32	0.943
I am skilled in constructing effective search queries to obtain accurate and useful results	168(46.5)	130(36)	27(7.5)	36(10)	3.19	0.951
Evaluation					3.31	0.868
I always evaluate the correctness of information before using them in my work.	201(55.7)	114(31.6)	22(6.1)	24(6.6)	3.36	0.868
I can distinguish between correct and unreliable information on textbooks and electronic resources.	188(52.1)	126(34.9)	31(8.6)	16(4.4)	3.35	0.816
I consider the currency and relevance of information when assessing its quality.	187(51.8)	111(30.7)	47(13)	16(4.4)	3.30	0.859
I read a textbook that follows syllabus and curriculum	190(52.6)	117(32.4)	23(6.4)	31(8.6)	3.29	0.923
I read a textbook that is detailed with perfect information	176(48.8)	133(36.8)	27(7.5)	25(6.9)	3.27	0.875
Application					3.29	0.886
I am confident in applying the	191(52.9)	131(36.3)	26(7.2)	13(3.6)	3.39	0.774

information I gather/read to solve problems.							
I always apply all ideas gathered in my assignments and examinations	203(56.2)	100(27.7)	49(13.6)	9(2.5)	3.38	0.811	
I effectively use the information resources retrieved in my library to do my assignments and update notes	197(54.6)	109(30.2)	20(5.5)	35(9.7)	3.30	0.951	
I gathered information for practical application	179(49.6)	117(32.4)	38(10.5)	27(7.5)	3.24	0.919	
I Integrate new information into my class note	165(45.7)	116(32.1)	45(12.5)	35(9.7)	3.14	0.976	
Overall Mean					3.34	0.858	

Source: Researcher's field work (2024)

Decision rule: if mean is 1-1.74= very low, 1.75-2.49= low, 2.5-3.24=high, 3.25-4.00=very high

Responses on level of information literacy skills of senior secondary school students in Ibadan North LGA are presented on Table 4. From the overall mean, it can be deduced that the level of information literacy skill of the students is very high on a 4-point scale (*Overall Mean = 3.34*, *SD = 0.858*). This implies that students in senior secondary schools in the LGA of study are highly information literate based on the data collected. The result further explains that respondents' information identification was also very high (*M=3.41*), as well as information searching (*M=3.34*), information evaluation (*M=3.31*), and application (*M=3.29*). Under identification, the respondents agreed that they can identify useful information resources (*M=3.59*), and compare information from various sources (*M=3.49*), as well as identify various view points of the topic from a textbook (*M=3.36*). On searching for information, the respondents agreed that they are confident in using phones/electronic tools to search for information (*M=3.45*), they are also aware of search techniques (Boolean operators, truncation, etc.) to enhance their search process (*M=3.41*), and are proficient in using search tools to find relevant information (*M=3.32*). In the same vein, the respondents on evaluation, indicated that they always evaluate the correctness of information before using them (*M=3.36*), as they can distinguish between correct and unreliable information on textbooks and electronic resources (*M=3.35*), while evaluating, they consider the currency and relevance of information when assessing its quality (*M=3.30*). Lastly, on application, the respondents indicated that they are confident in applying the information they gather/read to solve problems (*M=3.39*), they always apply all ideas gathered in their assignments and examinations (*M=3.38*), as well as effectively use the information resources retrieved in their libraries to do their assignments and update notes.

Research Question Two: What are the types of library resources used by students in public Secondary schools in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria?

Table 2 Types of library resources used

Resources	Never (%)	Rarely (%)	Occasionally (%)	Always (%)	Mean	SD
Novel	73(20.2)	57(15.8)	62(17.2)	169(46.8)	2.91	1.196
Text Books (Print textbooks)	78(21.6)	79(21.9)	51(14.1)	153(42.4)	2.77	1.208
Databases	112(31)	97(26.9)	80(22.2)	72(19.9)	2.31	1.112
Cartoons	186(51.5)	72(19.9)	43(11.9)	60(16.6)	1.94	1.140
Atlas	168(46.5)	100(27.7)	63(17.5)	30(8.3)	1.88	0.979
Newspaper (Print)	181(50.1)	89(24.7)	51(14.1)	40(11.1)	1.86	1.034
Electronic-books	224(62)	89(24.7)	32(8.9)	16(4.4)	1.56	0.832
Overall mean					2.18	1.07

Source: Researcher's field work (2024)

Decision rule: if mean is 1-1.74= not used, 1.75-2.49= rarely used, 2.5-3.24=highly used, 3.25-4.00=very highly used

The result as presented in Table 2 shows the types of library resources used by senior secondary class 3 students in Ibadan north LGA. The result revealed that novels ($M=2.91$), and textbooks ($M=2.77$) were highly used library resources. It also revealed that databases ($M=2.31$), cartoons ($M=1.94$), Atlas ($M=1.88$), and newspaper ($M=1.86$), were rarely used, while electronic books ($M=1.56$), were not used. This could mean that what is available to the students were the resources used as in the case of novels and textbooks.

Research question Three: What is the purpose of using library resources by students in public Secondary schools in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria?

Table 3 Purpose of library Resources Use

Purpose of Library Resources Use	Never (%)	Rarely (%)	Occasionally (%)	Always (%)	Mean	SD
To prepare for exams	18(5)	60(16.6)	54(15)	229(63.4)	3.37	.931
To revise my notes	35(9.7)	81(22.4)	65(18)	180(49.9)	3.08	1.052
For studying ahead of the class	52(14.4)	74(20.5)	56(15.5)	179(49.6)	3.00	1.132
To read and relax	44(12.2)	69(19.1)	105(29.1)	143(39.6)	2.96	1.037
For doing my assignments	66(18.3)	61(16.9)	63(17.5)	171(47.4)	2.94	1.172
Personal development	66(18.3)	68(18.8)	74(20.5)	153(42.4)	2.87	1.153
Overall mean					3.04	1.079

Source: Researcher's field work (2024)

Decision rule: if mean is 1-1.74 = very low, 1.75-2.49 = low, 2.5-3.24 = high, 3.25-4.00=very high
The purposes for use of library resources are presented on table 3 The result revealed that students use library resources to prepare for exams ($M=3.37$), revise their notes ($M=3.08$), study ahead of the class ($M=3.00$), to read and relax ($M=2.96$), for doing their assignments ($M=2.94$), and for personal development ($M=2.87$).

Table 4 Influence of information literacy skills on use of library resources

Variables	B	Std. Error	B	T	Sig.	R ²	Adj. R ²	F (df)	Anova Sig.
(Constant)	27.873	2.817		9.896	.000	.134	.124	(4, 356)	.000
Identification	.838	.231	.268	3.637	.000			13.792	
Searching	.208	.230	.076	.906	.366				
Evaluation	-.157	.250	-.057	-.628	.530				
Application	.303	.269	.112	1.127	.260				

Dependent Variable: Use of Library Resources

The result on the test of the influence of information literacy skills on library resources use by senior secondary school students in Oyo State is presented on Table 4. The result revealed that information literacy skills had significant influence on use of library resources of senior secondary school students ($Adj. R^2 = 0.124$, $F(4,356) = 13.792$, $p < 0.05$). This implies that the indicators of information literacy skills accounted for 12.4% variation in public secondary students' use of library resources and that the remaining 87.6% can be accounted for by variables not included in this model. The study further revealed that identification ($\beta = 0.268$, $t(356) = 3.367$, $p < 0.05$) had significant influence on students' use of library resources. However, searching ($\beta = 0.076$, $t(356) = 0.906$, $p > 0.05$), evaluation ($\beta = -.057$, $t(356) = -0.628$, $p > 0.05$), and application ($\beta = 0.112$, $t(356) = 1.127$, $p > 0.05$), were found to have no significant influence on students' use of library resources. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected and restated thus: Information literacy skills have significant influence on use of library resources by students in public secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Research question one identified the types of library resources used by students in public secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. The result as analysed in this study indicated that the types of library resources used more by students in public Secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria as novel, textbooks and databases while electronic books was the least used library resources. This study finding is quite similar to the findings of Okeuhie et al. (2021) which revealed that the most used library resources is textbooks although majority of the students never used electronic-books.

Research question two found out the purpose for which library resources are used for by students in public secondary school in Oyo State. The result obtained reveal that library resources was used for the purpose of preparing ahead of examination, studying ahead of the class and to revise my note while the least purpose of using the library was used for personal development. Thus, it could be deduced that the main purpose for the use of library resources by the public secondary students in the study area is for examination preparation. The study findings is quite different from the findings of Israel (2020), Jamogha et al., (2021) who conducted a study on library resources use and effectiveness by secondary school students at Oyemekun Grammar School, Akure, Ondo State and availability and utilisation of library information by students in selected secondary schools in Ondo West Local Government Area, Ondo State, Nigeria, respectively. In these studies, the main reason for the students' use of library resources was to acquire knowledge and do class assignments while only 8.0% and 46.88% showed interest in using library resources for examination preparation respectively. The difference may be attributed to the structure of the schools, personal quest for additional knowledge by the students and enlightenment of the students in the study areas. Research question three determined the level of information literacy skills of students in public Secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. The results obtained from the descriptive analysis revealed that the level of literacy skills was rated to be very high as most of the students strongly agreed that they can identify, search, evaluate and apply their literacy skills in the use of library resources respectively. The findings obtained in this study are similar to what Ladele et al. (2022) got in their study on information literacy skills and library use by JSS 111 students in Sagamu Local Government, Ogun State, Nigeria. From another perspective, Ekong and Ekong, 2018, Victor-Aigbodion, 2022 and Fakunle, 2023 obtained lower values among other category of students in their studies conducted on literacy proficiency. This present study establishes the fact that the senior secondary schools 3 have information literacy skills and as such can use it effectively in the selection of library resources.

Hypothesis one stated that information literacy skills have no significant influence on library resources use by students in public secondary schools in Oyo State, Nigeria. The findings established that information literacy skills have significant influence on library resources use by students in public secondary schools in Oyo State. The findings of this study align with the findings of Nwankwo (2023) that established a positive relationship between information literacy skills possessed by the students and their use of library resources. The ability to identify and search for relevant information to meet the current study need facilitate library use by students in public secondary schools in Oyo State.

CONCLUSION

The study analysed the influence of information literacy skills on library resources use by students in public secondary school in Oyo State, Nigeria. The study established that information literacy skills contributes to library resources use by public secondary school students in Oyo State.

Identification which is a factor of information literacy skills contribute significantly to library resources use. The study established that students visited the library to use resources such as novel, textbooks and database resources while electronic resources was not well used by the students. The study also established that the library resources were used for the purpose of preparing for examination, to revise note and studying ahead of their classes. But most of the students did not use the library for personal development. In conclusion, the study reveal that students in public secondary schools in Oyo State are information literate and use the library to prepare for exam and study ahead of the class.

RECOMMENDATION

1. The secondary school administration in collaboration with the school library board should ensure the availability and accessibility of electronic resources required for senior secondary school students in Oyo State, Nigeria.
2. Teachers and school librarian should promote the use of library resources in public secondary schools for personal development.
3. The school management should organise book club that will encourage the students in public secondary school desire to read in order to develop themselves at early years before proceeding to higher institution.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors have disclosed no conflicts of interest.

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